

TILNING INSONIYAT EVOLUTSIYASIDA TUTGAN O`RNI VA TARAQQIYOTI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqola tilning paydo bo`lishi kabi murakkab sotsiologik jarayonga oid bir nechta nazariyalar tahliliga bag`ishlangan. Unda Noam Xomskiy, Charlz Darvin, Maykl Tomasello, Maks Myuller va boshqa olimlarning tilning paydo bo`lishi haqidagi dastlabki qarashlariga ta`rif beriladi. Bundan tashqari tilning sotsiologik xususiyatlari haqida ham to`xtalib, uning odamlar orasidagi muloqotda tutgan o`rni ochib beriladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda insonlar orasida asosiy aloqa vositasi hisoblab kelinayotgan til bundan bir necha ming yillar oldin ibtidoiy odamlar nutqida bir nechta tovushlar talaffuzi timsolida namoyon bo`lgan edi. Inson evolutsiyasi jarayonida sayqallanib o`zining hozirgi mukammal va rangba-rang ko`rinishiga ega bo`ldi. Tilning paydo bo`lishi bir nechta taxminiy nazariyalarga asoslanadi: ¹

- **“Davomiylik nazariyasi”** odamning primat ajdodlari orasidagi tilning vujudga kelishidan oldingi muloqotning rivojlanishi kabi murakkab sotsiolingvistik jarayon natijasida til paydo bo`lgan degan gipotezani ilgari suradi;

- **“Spontan nazariya”** esa davomiylik nazariyasiga qarama-qarshi bo`lgan g`oyani ya`ni odam evolutsiyasi jarayonidagi

tasodifiy hodisa natijasida til paydo bo`lgan degan nazariyani qo`llab-quvvatlaydi;

- Ayrim nazariyalar tilga tabiiy genetik jarayonlar natijasi sifatida qaraydi;

- Bundan tashqari tilga ijtimoiy muloqot asosida o`rganiladigan ma`naviy sistema sifatida qarovchi bir nechta qarashlar ham mavjud.

2018-yilda ko`pchilik lingvistik olimlar “davomiylik nazariyasi” tarafdorlari edi, lekin ular til rivojlanishini qanday gipotezalashtirishda farqli xususiyatlarni ko`rsatadilar. Tilni asosan tug`ma xarakterga ega deb hisoblovchilar orasida ba`zilar inson bo`lmagan primatlarning til xususiyatlarini to`la ochib bera olmasliklarini aytadilar hamda til evolutsion taraqqiyot natijasi ekanligini ta`kidlab o`tadilar.² Ushbu intellektual faoliyat xodimlari orasida ko`pchilik,

¹ Ulbæk, Ib (1998). James R Hurford; Michael Studdert-Kennedy; Chris Knight (eds.). The origin of language and cognition. Approaches to the evolution of language : social and cognitive base. Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press. pp. 30–43.

² Pinker, Steven (1994). The language instinct. New York: W. Morrow and Co. ISBN 978-0-688-12141-9. OCLC 28723210

asosan, Ib Ulbaek³ til primatlarning bir-biri bilan muloqot qilishi natijasida emas, balki, bundanda murakkabroq jarayon bo'lgan primatlar kognatsiyasi hosilasidir degan fikrni qo'llab quvvatlaydilar.

Maykl Tomasello⁴ kabi tilga ijtimoiy muloqot natijasi sifatida qarovchilar primatlar orasidagi aloqaning kognitiv aspektlari natijasida rivojlanadi deb hisoblashadi hamda bu muloqot tovushlar vositasida emas, imo-ishoralar asosida yaratilgan. Tovushlar vositasidagi muloqot haqida gap ketganda, ko'plab nazariyotchilar insonning tildan qo'shiq kuylash uchun foydalanishini nazarda tutadilar.

"Spontan nazariya" tarafdori Noam Xomskiyning ta'kidlashicha, 100 000 yil oldin odam miyasida tasodifiy mutatsiya sodir bo'lib, til qobiliyatini "mukammal" yoki "yarim mukammal" holatga o'tkazgan⁵. Bir qator tarixiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, avstralopiteklar ham vokal muloqot qilish qobiliyatiga ega bo'lmagan. Ayrim olimlar primitiv til xususiyatlari rivojlanishi "Homo habilis" odam turi (2.5 million yil oldin) ning paydo bo'lishi bilan bog'liq deb taxmin qilishadi. Ramziy aloqa (belgilar orqali muloqot qilish) paydo bo'lishi esa "Homo erectus" (1.8 million yil oldin) ning paydo bo'lishi bilan bog'lanadi. Odamlar orasidagi aloqaning til vositasida olib borilishi esa

bundan 200,000 yil oldin "Homo sapiens" ning vujudga kelishi bilan baholanadi.⁶

Hozirgi zamonaviy tillarning tarqalishi va xilma-xillashuvi qaysi vaqtga borib taqalishini aniqlash uchun statistik metodlarni qo'llagan holda Kaliforniya universiteti tilshunosi Joanna Nikols 1998-yilda tovushlar vositagi (vocal) tillar bundan kamida 100 000 yil oldin xilma-xillashuvni boshlagan degan taxmini ilgari suradi.⁷

Q.D. Atkinson⁸ tomonidan olib borilgan keyingi tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, odamlarning afrikalik ajdodlari boshqa hududlarga ko'chib o'tganligi sababli ketma-ket populyatsiya to'siqlari paydo bo'lib, genetik va fenotipik xilma-xillikning pasayishiga olib keldi. Atkinsonning ta'kidlashicha, bu to'siqlar madaniyat va tilga ham ta'sir qilgan va ma'lum bir til Afrikadan qanchalik uzoqda bo'lsa, undagi fonemalar shunchalik kam bo'ladi. Dalil sifatida, Atkinsonning ta'kidlashicha, bugungi Afrika tillari nisbatan ko'p sonli fonemalarga ega, Okeaniya tillarida esa (odamlar yashaydigan oxirgi mintaqa) nisbatan kam.

³ Ulbaek, Ib (1998). James R Hurford; Michael Studdert-Kennedy; Chris Knight (eds.). The origin of language and cognition. Approaches to the evolution of language : social and cognitive base. Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press. pp. 30–43.

⁴ Tomasello, Michael (1996). B M Velichkovskii; Duane M Rumbaugh; Universität Bielefeld Zentrum für Interdisziplinäre Forschung (eds.). The cultural roots of language. Communicating meaning : the evolution and development of language. Mahwah, N.J.: L. Erlbaum.

⁵ Chomsky, N, 1996. Powers and Prospects. Reflections on human nature and the social order. London: Pluto Press, p 30.

⁶ Arcadi, AC. (August 2000). "Vocal responsiveness in male wild chimpanzees: implications for the evolution of language". Journal of Human Evolution. (2): 205–23.

⁷ Johanna Nichols, 1998. The origin and dispersal of languages: Linguistic evidence. In Nina Jablonski and Leslie C. Aiello, eds., The Origin and Diversification of Language, pp. 127–70. (Memoirs of the California Academy of Sciences, 24.) San Francisco: California Academy of Sciences.

⁸ Atkinson, Quentin (2011). "Phonemic Diversity Supports a Serial Founder Effect Model of Language Expansion from Africa". Science Magazine. (6027): 346–349.

Charlz Darvin⁹ tilning kelib chiqishini imo-ishoralar, turli xil tabiiy tovushlar, boshqa hayvonlarning ovozi va insonning instinktiv faryodlariga taqlid qilish va o'zgartirishga bog'liq ekanligini aytib o'tdi. 1861 yilda tarixiy tilshunos Maks Myuller og'zaki tilning kelib chiqishiga oid spekulativ nazariyalar ro'yxatini e'lon qildi:¹⁰

• **“Bov-vov”** - nemis faylasufi Iogann Gotfrid Xerderga tegishli bo'lgan faraz. Unga ko'ra dastlabki so'zlar hayvonlar va qushlarning qichqirig'iga taqlid qilish natijasida paydo bo'lgan. Ayrim adabiyotlarda “kakku” nazariyasi deb ham atiladi.

• **“Pooh-pooh”** – dastlabki so'zlarni og'riq, zavq, hayrat va hokazolar bilan qo'zg'atilgan hissiy so'zlar va undovlar sifatida paydo bo'lgan deb hisoblovchi nazariya.

• **“Ding-dong”** - Maks Myuller o'zining “ding-dong” deb nomlangan nazariyasini taklif qildi. Unga ko'ra hamma narsa tabiiy rezonans tebranishiga ega, bu esa inson tomonidan o'zining dastlabki so'zlarida qandaydir tarzda aks ettirilgan.

• **“Yo-he-ho”** – nazariyasi til paydo bo'lishini odamlarning jamoaviy ritmik mehnatdan so'ng hordiq chiqarish maqsadida, mushaklarning harakatini bo'shashtirishga urinish natijasida paydo bo'lganligini aytib o'tadi, natijada chuqur nafas olish holati “ho” taqlid tovushi bilan ifodalangan.

• **“Ta-ta”** nazariyasiga ko'ra, odamlar qo'lda imo-ishoralarni taqlid qilib, ularni eshitiladigan qilib ko'rsatadigan til

harakatlari orqali dastlabki so'zlarni yasagan.

Zamonaviy fanlar tizimida ko'pchilik olimlar bunday nazariyalarni unchalik to'g'ri deb hisoblamaydilar. Ularning fikricha, inson ajdodlari tovushlarni ma'nolar bilan bog'lash mexanizmini topganlaridan keyin, til avtomatik ravishda rivojlanib, o'zgargan.

O'rta asr musulmon olimlari ham tilning kelib chiqishi haqidagi bir nechta qarashlarni ishlab chiqdilar.¹¹ Ushbu nazariyalar beshta umumiy turdan iborat:

1. **Naturalistik nazariya:** Ifodalar bilan ular anglatgan narsalar o'rtasida tabiiy munosabat mavjud. Shuning uchun ham til insonning tabiat tovushlariga taqlid qilishga moyilligidan kelib chiqqan.

2. **Konvensionalistik nazariya:** Til ijtimoiy konvensiyadir. Narsalarning nomlari odamlarning tasodifiy ixtirolari natijasidir.

3. **Vahiy nazariyasi:** Til odamlarga Xudo tomonidan in'om etilgan va shuning uchun hamma narsani odamlar emas, balki Xudo nomlagan.

4. **Vahiychi-konvensionalistik nazariya:** Xudo odamlarga tilning asosiy bazasini ochib beradi, odamlarga bir-biri bilan muloqot qilish imkonini beradi. Shundan keyin odamlar tilning qolgan qismini ixtiro qildilar.

5. **Betaraf nazariya:** Konvensionalistik va vahiy nazariyalari bir xil darajada asosli deb hisoblovchi qarash.

Tilning paydo bo'lishi haqidagi mashhur nazariyalardan yana biri bu “ona tili”

⁹ Darwin, C. (1871). "The Descent of Man, and Selection in Relation to Sex, 2 vols. London: Murray, p. 56.

¹⁰ Müller, F. M. 1996 [1861]. The theoretical stage, and the origin of language. Lecture 9 from Lectures on the

Science of Language. Reprinted in R. Harris (ed.), The Origin of Language. Bristol: Thoemmes Press, pp. 7–41.

¹¹ Weiss, B. (1974). "[Medieval Muslim discussions of the origin of language](#)". Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft. 33–41.

gipotezasidir.¹² Unga ko`ra tillar dastlab faqat onalarga mansub bo`lgan. Ona o`z chaqalog`i bilan muloqotni yo`lga qo`yish maqsadida bolasiga tushunarli bo`lgan tovushlarni talaffuz qila boshlagan. Ikki tomonga ham tushunarli bo`lgan tovushlar so`z sifatida keyinchalik qabilaning boshqa

a`zolari orasida ham muloqot uchun ishlatila boshlandi. Shu tariqa qabila a`zolari orasida so`zlar vositasida muloqot qilish boshlangan.

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¹² Fitch, W. T. (2004). "[Kin selection and 'mother tongues': a neglected component in language evolution](#)" (PDF). In Ulrike Griebel; D Kimbrough Oller

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